

NonZero Rest Mass Free Particle Action from Electromagnetism?

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. April 11, 2022

The Lorentz transformation of (x,t) originally followed from an analysis of Maxwell's EM equations and included c the speed of light. Later in 1905 Einstein (1) developed an alternative derivation for a particle, but used a photon for measurement and so c again appeared

In a previous note (2) we argued that the classical action A for a free particle (nonzero rest mass) (relativistic $-m_0 \sqrt{1-vv/cc}$ or nonrelativistic $t.5movv$) may be written with $v=x/t$ and x and t varied independently leading to $-d/dx \text{ partial } A = p$ and $d/dt A = -E$. This leads to a solution $A = -Et+px$. One may note that the relativistic action contains c the speed of light which normally appears in electromagnetic theory.

In this note we examine how $A=-Et+px$ arises as a math solution of the electromagnetic continuity equation: $d/dt \text{ partial energy density} + d/dx \text{ Poynting vector} = 0$. Thus A has roots in Maxwell's electromagnetic equations, naturally includes c and is linked to Lorentz transformations. It may also be seen that A represents two dispersion relationships: $dA=0 = -E dt + p dx$ which pertains to light and classical waves and $dA=0 = -t dE + x dp$. If this second case is linked with $p=Ev$ which is the dispersion relationship for a particle with rest mass, one may show that $E=m_0cc/ \sqrt{1-vv/cc}$ using $dp/dE = (dp/dv)/ (dE/dv)$. Thus we argue that $A=-Etc + pxc$ follows from electromagnetism hence " c " appears, but is consistent with two dispersion relationships, one for light (or a classical wave) and the other for a particle with nonzero rest mass i.e. $p=Ev$.

Special Relativity

Special relativity emerged with Lorentz finding x,t transformations which kept Maxwell's electromagnetic equations of the same form. As a result, this transformation included c the speed of light in a vacuum which follows from a classical wave equation for a photon. This in turn follows from Maxwell's equations without sources. In 1905, Einstein provided an alternative derivation (1) focusing on particle motion, but using light as a measuring object. As a result, properties of light (i.e its constant velocity in different moving frames) as well as its vacuum value affect the result, in particular c appears. Thus special relativity is closely linked to electromagnetism historically.

Classical Action of a Free Particle

The idea of momentum $p=m_0 v$ where m_0 is rest mass and v velocity was presented by Newton in the late 1600s. In the late 1700s, Lagrange introduced a Lagrangian such that $p=dL/dv \text{ partial}$. Furthermore, Lagrange equations follow from insisting the classical action $\text{Integral } dt L$ be stationary. In a previous note (2) we noted that if one writes $v=x/t$ for either a nonrelativistic $A=t.5 m_0 vv$ or relativistic $-m_0 t \sqrt{1-vv/cc}$ action one may find, treating x and t as independent:

$$dA/dx \text{ partial} = p \text{ ((1a)) and } dA/dt \text{ partial} = -E \text{ ((1b))}$$

We argued that one thinks in terms of flow in such a case. The nonrelativistic result does not contain c , the vacuum speed of light, but the relativistic form does. This begs the question: Why is the speed of light present for a particle with nonzero rest mass? No electromagnetic considerations have been made. As a consequence we consider Maxwell's electromagnetic equations.

Maxwell's Electromagnetic Equations

Maxwell, in the mid- late 1800s, wrote electromagnetic equations for E the electric field and B the magnetic. As a result, it may first appear that these equations have nothing to do with dynamics. Maxwell, however, obtained a classical wave equation for both E and B from these em equations with a solution of the form $\sin(-Et+px)$. He argued that this result applied to light which has a vacuum speed linked to ϵ_0 and μ_0 , parameters in his equation. His result matched the known value of 3×10^8 m/s. Maxwell's equations without sources also allow one to write a dynamical flux equation:

$$\frac{d}{dt} \text{partial} (.5\epsilon_0 E E + .5\mu_0 B B) + \text{grad dot} (1/\mu_0 E \times B) = 0 \quad ((2))$$

The first term in brackets is energy density and the second momentum flux. This may be analogously written as:

$$A = -Ect + pcx \text{ such that } \frac{dA}{dt} \text{partial} + \frac{dA}{dx} \text{partial} = 0 \text{ or } E = pc \quad ((3))$$

One may note that $\frac{dA}{dx} \text{partial} = p$ and $\frac{dA}{dt} \text{partial} = -E$ $c = 1/\sqrt{\epsilon_0 \mu_0}$

$E = pc$ is the dispersion relationship for light. It is also linked to:

$dA = 0 = -E dt + p dx$ or $c = dx/dt = E/p$ which is the dispersion relationship for a classical wave. It is interesting to note, however, that A ((3)) is consistent with a second dispersion relationship: $p = Ev$ ((4)). For this to hold, however, $E = \frac{m_0 v}{\sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}}$ which is the result of special relativity. Special relativity is already known to be consistent with Maxwell's electromagnetic equations so $p = Ev$ is consistent with this.

((4)) has the appearance of a dispersion relationship for a particle with nonzero rest mass e.g. the Newtonian nonrelativistic $p = m_0 v$. One may note that for ((3)) $E = pc$ implies that if $p = 0$, $E = 0$ so there is no rest mass in this situation, but ((4)) allows for $E \rightarrow m_0$ if $v \rightarrow 0$.

A nonzero rest implies one has a free particle with rest mass i.e. classical mechanics, but A ((3)) is a result which follows from electromagnetism and is linked with c , the speed of light in a vacuum. The link becomes stronger if one considers Lagrange's result:

$$dL/dv \text{partial} = p = \frac{d}{dx} (L_t) \quad dx/dv = \frac{dA}{dx} \text{partial} \quad ((5))$$

Thus Lagrange's result (which is nonrelativistic) is linked to the fuller relativistic (Lorentz invariant form) $A = -Et + px$ ((3)) which has electromagnetic origins. No c appears in ((5)).

One may note that for a nonrelativistic free particle with rest mass:

$$A = t \cdot \frac{1}{2} m \frac{xx}{t^2} = -Et + px = -\frac{1}{2} m \frac{xx}{t} + m \frac{xx}{t} \quad ((6))$$

The electromagnetic continuity equation ((2)) and its analogue ((3)) are linked to the dispersion relationship for a classical wave. The solution $A = -Et + px$, however, allows for two dispersion solutions, one for a classical wave and the other for a particle with nonzero rest mass. In the latter case, one has the two flux relationships ((1a)) and ((1b)) together with $p = Ev$. As shown in a previous note, one may use these to find the form of special relativity (although it may also be found using Lorentz's approach for the Maxwell's equations of that of (1)). The goal is to find a differential equation for $L(v)$ and hence find L (3):

$$E = \text{Hamiltonian} = pv - L, \quad p = Ev \quad \text{and} \quad p = dL/dv \quad \text{yielding} \quad (1/v) dL/dv = v dL/dv - L$$

$$\text{With a solution} \quad L = -m_0 \sqrt{1 - vv/cc} \quad ((7))$$

The cc ensures vv/cc is dimensionless, but cc ultimately follows from the electromagnetic result ((3)).

One may note that: $p = dL/dv$ partial is equivalent to $p = dA(v)/dx$ partial = $d tL(v)/d(vt)$ with t a constant when one takes the partial with respect to t . Furthermore $A = Lt = -Et + px$ ((3)) is equivalent to: $L = -E + pv$ so the results of ((7)) follow from the two flow flux equations dA/dx partial = p and dA/dt partial = $-E$ and $p = Ev$.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that although one may take the classical action forms for a free particle with nonzero rest mass: $\frac{1}{2} m_0 v^2$ (nonrelativistic) and $-m_0 \sqrt{1 - vv/cc}$ relativistic and write $v = x/t$ to obtain dA/dx partial = p and dA/dt partial = $-E$ with solution $A = -Et + px$, this solution follows from electromagnetism. As a result, there is a reason for c , the speed of light in a vacuum appearing in the relativistic case i.e. vv/cc . If one considers the Poynting continuity equation: d/dt energy density + grad dot Poynting vector = 0, it is equivalent to:

$$dA/dt \text{ partial} + dA/dx \text{ partial} = 0 \quad \text{with} \quad A = -E ct + pc x \quad \text{as a solution.}$$

This result has the dispersion relationship $dA=0 = -E dt + pc dx$ or $dx/dt = E/p = c$ for a classical wave in this case light. There is another possible dispersion relationship, however, namely $1/v = dp/dE = (dp/dv) / (dE/dv)$. If one tries to link this to a $p = Ev$ which is similar to Newton's $p = mv$ for the nonrelativistic case, then $A = -Et + px$ leads to the special relativistic form $p = mv/\sqrt{1 - vv/cc}$ and $E = m_0 cc/\sqrt{1 - vv/cc}$. " C " the speed of light in a vacuum is used to ensure variables have the proper dimension. $A = -Et + px$ follows from electromagnetism ((3)), but

one may find that it is equivalent to both the nonzero rest mass free particle classical actions: (nonrelativistic) $\frac{1}{2}m_0 v^2$ and (relativistic) $-m_0 c \sqrt{1-v^2/c^2}$ with $v=x/t$. Thus we argue that c and the form $A=-Et+px$ follow from electromagnetism.

References

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